

FEATURES OF HEMOSTASIS DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CORONAVIRUS IN THE KHOREZM REGION

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Introduction: *COVID-19 is associated with severe thrombotic complications, both micro- and macrovascular lesions, mainly deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, primary pulmonary artery thrombosis, up to a syndrome similar to intravascular coagulation.*

The purpose of the study: *To study the features of hemostasiological disorders in patients with coronavirus during the first wave of COVID-19.*

Methods: *Hemostasiological studies were conducted in 115 COVID-19 patients treated in the cuvette department of the Khorezm regional Multidisciplinary Center for the period 2019-2020.*

Results: The degree of hypercoagulation syndrome and the risk of thrombosis depend on the severity of COVID-19. The data obtained indicate the presence of hypercoagulation, which is confirmed by a statistically significant shortening of VSC by more than two times (compared with the control group 248.0 ± 6.8 to 118.2 ± 7.4) and APTT by 1.5 times (up to 28 ± 2.1 versus 43 ± 1.0), an increase in the level of RFMC among COVID-19 patients by almost two three times. The average TV value compared to the control group turned out to be 1.6 times longer, and the average amount of fibrinogen exceeded its level in comparison with the control by 1.8 times.

Conclusion: The results obtained in COVID-19 patients indicate a state of hypercoagulation, as evidenced by an increase in the concentration of a number of plasma coagulation factors in the blood and an increase in fibrin degradation products.